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Three-point bending and impact behaviours of grass fibre-reinforced castor oil composites

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Abstract: This work investigates the physical and mechanical properties of grass (*Cynodon* spp.) fibre-reinforced composites made with castor-oil polyurethane (BioPU). The composites are manufactured by cold pressing at 645 kPa with two random fibre configurations (long and ground). The three-point bending and Charpy impact tests are performed after 14 days of curing time. Analysis of variance is performed to assess the effect of fibre aspect ratio on responses. The findings are compared with randomised short coir-fibre biocomposites, available in the literature, composed of a similar matrix phase. Ground fibres possess superior mechanical properties due to their enhanced homogeneity and lower void volume. Ground grass fibre-BioPU achieves the highest flexural modulus (1.59 GPa), approximately 74.7% greater than coir-BioPU (0.91 GPa) and 39.47% greater than long grass fibre-BioPU (1.14 GPa). In contrast, impact resistance is higher for coir-BioPU (22.76 kJ/m²), corresponding to ~136.59% and ~135.37% increase over long grass-fibre BioPU and ground grass-fibre BioPU, respectively.

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1. Introduction

Environmental concerns have boosted the development of bio-based composite materials. Grass fibres, in particular, have been considered a potential reinforcement for polymer composites by many researchers [1-4]. Natural fibres, based on cellulose, are biodegradable, non-toxic, low-cost, non-abrasive and lightweight, low

combustibility natural resources [5]. Tifton 85 (*Cynodon* spp.) is one of the most used grasses for hay and animal feedstock. According to Silva (2019), the herbage production of tropical grasses is marked by seasonality, with large and fast growth in the rainy period and small and slow growth during the dry season; however, in the tropical conditions, these pastures can be managed under rotational stocking [6].

The thermal properties of nano-clay-enriched, wild cane-grass fibre-reinforced polyester composites have been recently investigated at different fibre volume fractions [1]. The results indicate that the composite is lightweight with good thermal properties and can be used in the construction and aerospace industries. *Saccharum spontaneum* (Kans grass) fibre properties were also analysed considering applications on polymeric materials. Tests were conducted on untreated and treated fibres at different concentrations of alkali treatment. Results show that the 5% alkali treatment achieves better thermal and mechanical fibre properties, similar to other natural fibres used in lightweight polymer composites [2].

Further work was done by Mori et al. [3] to evaluate an Ichu-grass fibre-reinforced polyester composite. Fibres were cut as a unidirectional reinforcement, considering a fibre volume fraction of 38%. Transverse and longitudinal flexural tests revealed flexural strength and modulus of 144 MPa and 8.8 GPa in the longitudinal direction, and 31 MPa and 3 GPa, respectively, in the transverse direction

In line with sustainable development, bio-based resins have been considered substitutes for petroleum-based polymers. Baroncini et al. lists 26 bio-based epoxy resins and curing agents and their main properties and potential applications [4]. Adenkule et al. [5] proposed a bio-based composite using a novel thermoset resin from soybean oil. Composites were fabricated based on three different types of functionalised soybean oil resins from renewable origins with flax fibres as reinforcement. The authors evaluated their properties through impact, flexural testing and Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) of knife-cut cross-sections to investigate the fibre–matrix interface. The results indicate that soybean-oil polymers can potentially replace petrochemical-based conventional matrices in natural-fibre composites.

This work describes the fabrication of composites made with Tifton 85 grass hay (*Cynodon* spp.) and castor-oil polyurethane matrix, their physical (water absorption, apparent density and porosity) and mechanical characterisation (under flexural and impact loads).

2. Methodology

Composite samples are manufactured with a castor-oil based biopolymer (AGT 1315), composed of components B (polyol) and A (diisocyanate) mixed at a mass fraction of 1.2:1, supplied by Imperveg - Brazil, and Tifton 85 grass hay (*Cynodon* spp.), provided by Deflor Bioengenharia - Brazil. Random grass fibres are incorporated considering two configurations - long fibres (in a mat-like arrangement) and ground short fibres. Based on preliminary fabrication tests, the fibre-matrix volume fraction is set at 40/60 to ensure full-fibre wettability and avoid resin leakage.

The process adopted is the hand lay-up and uniaxial cold compaction techniques. Hay fibres are hand-mixed with the polymer resin, and the mixture is subsequently placed on an aluminium plate (0.5 mm thickness) inside a steel mould frame (310 × 310 × 3 mm³). A similar aluminium plate is placed on the top surface, and the mould is

closed with a steel lid. The laminates are cured for 60 h at room temperature ($\sim 22^{\circ}\text{C}$) under constant uniaxial pressure of 645 kPa. This pressure level is established based on preliminary studies [7, 8]. A release agent is spread over the aluminium surfaces to obtain a composite plate with a smooth surface finish. Composites about 3 mm thick are post-cured at room temperature ($\sim 22^{\circ}\text{C}$) for two weeks.

Hay-fibre reinforced PU composites are tested for water absorption (ASTM D570) [9], apparent density and porosity (ASTM C1039-85) [10], three-point bending (ASTM D790-15) [11] and Charpy impact (ASTM D6110-10) [12]. At least four samples are produced per condition for each proposed test with two replicates. A Shimadzu AGX testing machine equipped with a 100 kN load cell is used to perform the bending tests at 2 mm/min. Impact tests are conducted on an XJJ Series Charpy Impact Tester. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and Tukey's test are used to evaluate the hay fibre length (long and short) effect on the impact resistance, flexural modulus, and strength. The findings are compared to those obtained for coir-BioPU composites reported by Braga et al. (2021) [13], fabricated using a similar methodology.

3. Results and Discussions

3.1. Physical and mechanical properties

Table 1. Physical and mechanical properties of the investigated composites.

	Water Absorption		Apparent Density		Porosity		Flexural Modulus		Flexural Strength		Impact Resistance	
	%	Tukey	(g/cm ³)	Tukey	%	Tukey	GPa	Tukey	MPa	Tukey	kJ/m ²	Tukey
Long Grass BioPU	39.6 (± 4.2)	A	0.93 (± 0.04)	B	25.3 (± 1.7)	A	1.14 (0.00)	B	11.57 (± 0.63)	B	9.62 (± 0.19)	B
Short Grass BioPU	18.1 (± 2.3)	C	1.14 (± 0.05)	A	16.99 (± 1.29)	B	1.59 (± 0.11)	A	17.23 (± 0.35)	A	9.67 (± 0.26)	B
Coir BioPU	24.7 (± 2.3)	B	0.73 (± 0.05)	C	15.38 (± 0.79)	B	0.91 (± 0.08)	B	16.33 (± 0.44)	A	22.8 (± 1.6)	A
p-Value	<u>0.000</u>		<u>0.000</u>		<u>0.000</u>		<u>0.008</u>		<u>0.003</u>		<u>0.001</u>	
p _{AD}	0.304		0.171		0.385		0.569		0.216		0.378	
R ² (Adj) %	86.88		92.57		91.95		93.31		96.82		98.09	

Table 1 shows the mean values for the physical and mechanical properties of the fabricated bio-composites considering replicates 1 and 2. Analysis of variance results along with Tukey's test are presented. Effects are considered significant for $P \leq 0.05$ (underlined values). P values for the Anderson Darling test ($P_{AD} \geq 0.05$) confirm the normality of the data, and $R^2(\text{adj})$ (from 86.88% to 98.09%) values indicate the good predictability of the underlying statistical model used.

Water absorption is $\sim 102.27\%$ and $\sim 48.02\%$ higher for long grass-biopolymer composites compared to short Grass-BioPU and Coir-BioPU, respectively (Figure 1a). The lower water absorption of short-fibre composites can be attributed to a lower diffusion capacity, owing to the more homogeneous structure with a higher packing level [14, 15] relative to long fibre composites. Short grass fibre-BioPU achieves higher apparent density (1.14 g/cm³),

~56.16% greater than coir-BioPU (0.93 g/cm³) and ~22.58% greater than long grass-fibre-BioPU (0.73 g/cm³) (Figure 1b). The porosity is statistically equivalent for short-grass-fibre-BioPU and coir-BioPU, which are ~64.56% and ~48.97% respectively lower than long-grass-biopolymer composites (Figure 1c).

Short-fibre grass composites possess superior flexural properties due to their enhanced homogeneity and lower void volume. Short grass fibre-BioPU achieves higher flexural modulus (1.59 GPa), ~74.73% greater than coir-BioPU (0.91 GPa) and ~39.47% greater than long grass fibre-BioPU (1.14 GPa) (Figure 1d). The fibre length factor has a great influence on the flexural modulus behaviour. The mixture is based on weight-fraction, and ground grass fibres present a greater amount of matrix phase, which provides better fibre-matrix bonding. The long grass BioPU presented lower flexural strength, ~48.92% and ~41.14% lower when compared to Short Grass BioPU and Coir BioPU, respectively (Figure 1e). This finding may be caused by its higher heterogeneity and greater void volume ratio, contributing to stress concentration and premature failure of the composite.

Figure 1. Main effects plots for Water Absorption (a), Apparent Density (b), Porosity (c), Flexural Modulus (d), Flexural Strength (e), and Impact Resistance (f)

In contrast, impact resistance is higher for coir-BioPU (22.76 kJ/m²), corresponding to ~136.59% and ~135.37% increase over long grass fibre BioPU and ground grass fibre-BioPU, respectively (Figure 1f). Coir fibre is known for its high level of tenacity and strain; therefore, impact resistance is greatly affected when coir fibre is used [16].

3. Conclusions

Cynodon-reinforced castor-oil composites have been fabricated and characterised. The grass fibre length factor at the levels investigated significantly affects physical and flexural properties. The impact resistance, however, is not significantly affected. The flexural modulus of short grass-fibre composites is ~74.7% greater than coir-BioPU and ~39.47% greater than long grass-fibre-BioPU, which is attributed to improved dispersion within the matrix phase. Long grass-BioPU composites presented flexural strength ~48.92% and ~41.14% lower relative to short-grass-BioPU and Coir-BioPU, respectively. This finding may be caused by its higher heterogeneity and higher void volume ratio, which contributes to stress concentration and premature failure. Impact resistance is higher for

coir-BioPU, corresponding to ~136.59% and ~135.37% increase over long-grass-BioPU and short-grass-BioPU, respectively. The higher impact resistance obtained for coir-BioPU may be related to its higher level of tenacity and strain; therefore, impact resistance is greatly affected when coir fibre is used.

The application of *Cynodon*-reinforced castor-oil composites as a core material in Fibre-Metal Laminates (FML) will be the scope of future investigations.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

CRedit author statement

GG Braga: Methodology /Writing – original draft. **JC dos Santos:** Data curation; Software. **FA Rosa:** Formal analysis; Data curation. **LJ da Silva:** Writing – original draft. **RTS Freire:** Writing – review. **TH Panzera:** Conceptualisation; Supervision; Writing – review/ Resources.

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